

IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF ENTERPRISES PROBLEMS AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract: This in the article enterprises efficiency increase issues , current problems and there is opportunities analysis Also , efficiency increase for modern management approaches , innovative from technologies use and optimal resource management methods seeing is released . Article in the end relevant recommendations given .

Key words: enterprise efficiency , management , innovation , problems , opportunities , resources management

Introduction. Enterprises efficiency not only of the enterprise himself/herself for , maybe of the economy general development also important for importance has . Today globalization and competition environment from enterprises high at the level flexibility and efficiency demand This is in the article enterprises efficiency in progress important problems and opportunities analysis will be done .

Trade enterprises activity effective organization to do , first of all management to the effectiveness directly related is considered . Trade enterprises effective management the process first in line this the enterprise management methods and principles how much based on with is determined . In this trade of the enterprise management to the effectiveness achieve success in the following that is, management social importance , management in progress cultivated of the product profitability , consumers and markets about of information sufficiency , trade technology , organization goods with related concept , image and other this etc. important importance profession will reach¹.

Analysis and results . Efficiency is desired the result to take is the ability . If any thing effective that if found , this his/her expected or unexpected to the result has that or deep , bright impression leave means². Enterprise efficiency this most efficient use of resources use through high economic to the results is to achieve . This concept economic efficiency , financial stability, production release power and human resources efficiency such as elements own inside takes .

The word "**efficiency**" is the result said meaning gives . Enterprises dedicated to the economy most in literature working of release only cost-effectiveness about word goes . However , in the country event given social changes of people attention attraction is doing and socio-economic processes study and to them price to give necessity is giving birth . Today on the day working both economic and social efficiency study extreme important . They mutual integral related and each other requirement enough are categories .

Enterprises efficiency increase on the way one row problems there is :

- **Resources wrong management** : Many in enterprises resources at optimal levels not used .

- **Technological backwardness** : Innovative from technologies not to use working release process efficiency reduces .
- **Staff qualification low** : Modern under the circumstances enough knowledge and to skills has of personnel shortage problem gives birth .
- **Financial restrictions** : Investments and financial of resources shortage to develop obstacle does .

Enterprise efficiency increase for following from opportunities use possible:

- **Innovative technologies current to** : Modern technologies working release size increase and expenses to reduce help gives .
- **Human resources development** : Staff qualification increase through of the enterprise competitiveness reinforcement possible .
- **Good management systems** : Operation efficiency provide for modern management from the approaches use important .
- **International from experience study** : Other countries experience study and adaptation through to success achieve possible .
- In enterprises digital technologies current to grow for special programs working exit need .
- Staff qualification to increase aimed at trainings organization to grow necessary .
- Resources management modern methods current to grow necessary .
- Innovative to entrepreneurship additional encouragement mechanisms create important .

Above our thoughts to the table we place :

Table 1

<i>Problems</i>	<i>Opportunities</i>
<i>Resources wrong management</i>	<i>Innovative technologies current to grow</i>
<i>Technological backwardness</i>	<i>Human resources develop</i>
<i>Staff qualification low</i>	<i>Good management systems</i>
<i>Financial restrictions</i>	<i>International from experience study</i>

Developing market economy under the circumstances of the state economic strategy far to time the fundamental objectives intended to the middle to put with one in the row , this to goals achieve means , ways also define it yourself inside takes . These between working release efficiency non-stop increasing to go main in place stands . Every how social in society working release efficiency increase economic of progress basis creates . Uzbekistan of the state power strengthening , population material and spiritual to blessings was needs full

satisfaction , in the future and them abundant creation , economic and scientific and technical most advanced in the field countries to take a seat in the queue working release efficiency to increase directly is related.

Conclusion . Enterprises efficiency increase today's of the day current from issues is one . This in the article analysis made problems and opportunities based on efficiency increase according to practical recommendations working Modern technologies and management from the approaches use through enterprises not only own efficiency, but economic of the system general also ensure the development takes .

Enterprises activity interests newest for opportunities and from necessities one the enterprise technical and technological processes further develop way with efficiency increase through real economy of the republic in networks to the body come remaining shortage prevent to take and promising to progress opportunity is to create.

Enterprise efficiency increase economic development important condition is, this process many edged approach demand will reach . First next , technological updates current to be done , this and working release processes speed and product quality Also , qualified personnel attraction to do and them regular accordingly develop of the enterprise competitiveness Digital management systems application from resources effective use opportunity creates . From this outside , international experience study and local to the conditions adaptation through enterprises own strategies optimization possible .

Above emphasized all measures done If increased , enterprises economic stability provide with one in a row , general economic too big to grow contribution Addictive . Efficiency increase not only benefit to take opportunities expands , maybe national of the economy innovative potential to increase service does . So so , today of the day current needs and competition in the environment enterprises own activities permanent accordingly improving they go necessary .

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